

Changes in rice area, production, and yield after the introduction of varieties of the new plant type. Punjab Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Year	Area planted to rice (1000 ha)	Area planted to semidwarf varieties		Production of milled rice (1000 t)	Yield (t/ha)
		(1000 ha)	(%)		
1950	120	-	-	107	0.79
1955	149	-	-	107	0.72
1960	227	-	-	220	1.1
1965	292	-	-	292	1.0
1966	285	4	1	338	1.2
1967	314	17	5	415	1.3
1968	345	27	8	470	1.4
1969	350	72	20	535	1.5
1970	390	143	38	688	1.8
1971	450	311	73	920	2.0
1972	476	378	79	955	2.0
1973	498	450	84	1140	2.1
1974	570	500	88	1181	2.1
1975	566	500	91	1445	2.6

in 1969, and Palman 579 (IR579-48-1-2) in 1971—the rice crop in the state changed progressively (see table). The area under high-yielding varieties (HYV) increased from 1 percent in 1966 to more than 90 percent in 1975. Correspondingly, rice yield increased from 1.2 to 2.6 t/ha. Total area in rice also increased from 285,000 to 566,000 ha and rice is now being grown on soils where other kharif crops were previously grown. All these factors—particularly the area under HYV—are

responsible for an increase in rice production in the state from 292,000 tons in 1965 to 1,445,000 tons in 1975—about a fivefold increase. Because the majority of the Punjab population do not consume rice, most of the state's production is saved for the Central Rice Pool. In 1975, the Punjab made the highest contribution of any state, 1,100,000 tons of rice, which made up more than 35 percent of the pool.

A new rice variety, Kranti, bred by Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University Research Station, Raipur

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A new rice variety, Kranti (sel. no. R 2022), has been developed by the Central Rice Research Station, Raipur,

India, working under Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Madhya Pradesh. It derives from the cross C-116/IR8. C-116 is a variety bred from a cross between two local varieties, Bhondu and Parewa. Kranti is slightly taller than Jaya (105 vs. 95 cm) so it does better under rainfed conditions than other semidwarfs. Under irrigated conditions

Mean paddy yield of Kranti (R 2022) in several villages. Rice Research Station, Raipur, India.

Variety	Paddy yield (kg/ha)			
	1974		1975	
	Irrigated	Nonirrigated	Irrigated	Nonirrigated
Kranti (R 2022)	4813	1739	6812	4537
Ratna	3890	1499	-	-
Anupama	-	-	5689	3204
C.D. 5%	607	-	428	399

it has also yielded higher than Ratna or Jaya. Kranti matures in 120 days when planted in kharif (June-October) so it fits well into double and multiple cropping patterns.

Its grain is short and bold with shiny strawcolored husk. Its cooking quality is good. Kranti has field resistance to bacterial blight, blast, and false smut.

The RD series of rice varieties developed in Thailand from 1969 to 1975

Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, Thailand

The release of the RD (Rice Division) series of varieties began in 1969 with RD1, RD2, and RD3 and has now progressed to RD9. Glutinous varieties are denoted by even numbers. So far, all releases are essentially insensitive to photoperiod, fall into the general classification of high-yielding varieties, and conform to the Thai grain standards for class 1 milled grain.

The most widely grown new variety is RD1 (LT/IR8). More than 70 percent of the dry-season planting in irrigated areas is estimated to be devoted to it. In recent years, however, its spread has been slowed by bacterial blight and, recently, by brown planthoppers in some fields.

RD2 (TN1/Gam Pai 15) was intended for the areas of north and northeast Thailand where consumers prefer glutinous rice. But it has not been popular among farmers in the northeast, probably because it is short and lacks photoperiod sensitivity. Susceptibility to bacterial blight and to gall midge may also limit its use.

RD3 (LT/IR8) was intended for areas where farmers apply only minimal inputs of fertilizer and other management practices. Data collected before its release suggest that it competes better with weeds and produces higher yields than RD1 at low fertilizer levels. But RD3 has not found favor with most farmers, probably because of its extreme susceptibility to bacterial blight, and long flag leaves that prevent easy visibility of panicles.